

IET10522, a high-yielding, medium-duration rice for waterlogged conditions

G. Nallathambi, S. Sevugaperumal, J. G. Robinson, and A. S. Mathar, Agricultural Research Station, Thirupathisaram 629901, Tamil Nadu, India

In Kalkulam and Vilavancode taluks of Kanyakumari district, nearly 10,000 ha of ricefields are waterlogged in both the wet and dry seasons. Standing water depth ranges from 15 to 30 cm throughout the cropping period.

We evaluated four deepwater rice cultures and medium-deep varieties ADT40, CO 42, and H4 for 3 yr, 1987-88 to 1989-90. The trial was laid out in 4 ×

Performance of waterlogging-tolerant cultures at Agricultural Research Station, Thirupathisaram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1987-88 to 1989-90.

Variety	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)				Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	Straw yield (t/ha)
		1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	Mean					
IET10522	RP31-49-2/LMN	4.9	4.1	4.2	4.4	140	102	8	2.19	12.2
IET10205	Manasarovar/CO 14	2.9	3.2	2.4	2.8	130	132	7	1.08	12.3
IET10207	Manasarovar/CO 14	2.2	2.4	1.8	2.1	138	90	7	0.99	10.0
IET10208	RP31-49-2/LMN	2.9	2.6	2.0	2.5	138	94	7	1.20	10.5
H4	—	3.4	2.2	2.3	2.7	137	92	7	1.10	8.4
ADT40	Sona/RP6/13	3.6	3.4	3.1	3.4	138	97	8	1.38	10.0
CO 42	RP31-49-2/LMN	3.5	3.5	2.9	3.3	139	119	8	1.17	9.3
LSD (0.05)		0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5					1.1

3-m plots, with 20 × 10-cm spacing, in a randomized block design with three replications. The nursery was raised in Sep and transplanting was in Oct.

IET10522 (RP31-49-2/LMN) was found promising in all 3 yr (see table).

Mean grain yield was 4.4 t/ha. Yields were 29.5 and 33.8% higher than yields of ADT40 and CO 42, respectively.

IET10522 is medium tall, nonlodging, with long slender white grains. ■

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Influence of mycorrhizal association and inorganic nutrients on early growth of rice

S. S. Dhillon, Biological Sciences Department, Illinois State University, Normal, Illinois 61761, USA; and L. Ampornpan, Biological Sciences Department, Srinakharinwirot University, Bangkok, Thailand

We examined the vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM) fungal association of young rice plants and its response to inorganic nutrients.

Seeds of rice variety Lebonnet were obtained from the Louisiana State University Rice Research Station (LSURRS). VAM fungal inoculum (rice roots and rhizosphere soil) was obtained by growing rice plants in soil from LSURRS.

Plants were grown to the early growth stage (50 d) in sterilized soil with mycorrhizal (VAM) and without mycorrhizal (NON-VAM) propagules and supplied with 2.5 ml of nutrient solution at 160 µg/g (nutrient availability after application = 11.2 µg/g) applied every 7 d. Nutrient treatments were P, N, P + N, and deionized water (control).

Table 1. Root and shoot dry weight of rice grown in sterilized soil with inorganic nutrients and VAM fungi.^a

Nutrient treatment	Root dry weight (g)		Shoot dry weight (g)	
	Without VAM	With VAM	Without VAM	With VAM
Phosphorus	1.21 ± 0.31 b	0.44 ± 0.10 a	1.48 ± 0.44 b	0.53 ± 0.12 a
Nitrogen	0.74 ± 0.12 a	0.59 ± 0.09 a	0.80 ± 0.15 a	0.58 ± 0.13 a
Phosphorus + nitrogen	1.25 ± 0.27 b	0.29 ± 0.15 a	1.28 ± 0.25 b	0.37 ± 0.26 a
Deionized water	1.44 ± 0.37 b	0.39 ± 0.23 a	1.42 ± 0.27 b	0.59 ± 0.23 a

^a Mean (X ± SD). In a column, means with the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's mean separation test (p < 0.05).

Plants were watered daily for moisture conditions similar to those of rice seedlings growing in nonflooded fields.

Plants grown in NON-VAM sterilized soil and supplied with P, P + N, and deionized water had significantly higher root and shoot dry weights than plants grown in soil with VAM fungi and the same nutrients (Table 1). There were no differences between the plants supplied with N alone, with or without VAM.

Control plants supplied with deionized water had significantly higher fungi colonization than all other treatments (Table 2).

Plants inoculated with VAM fungi and supplied with P, P + N, and deionized water had significantly lower root and shoot biomass than plants grown in soil without VAM but with the same nutrients. In the NON-VAM treatments, plants

Table 2. VAM colonization of rice roots grown in sterilized soil with inorganic nutrients and VAM fungi inoculum.^a

Nutrient treatment	VAM colonization (%)
Phosphorus	29.76 ± 9.87 a
Nitrogen	32.00 ± 6.53 a
Phosphorus + nitrogen	27.83 ± 7.10 a
Deionized water	43.65 ± 11.33

^a Mean (X ± SD). Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's mean separation test (p < 0.05).

supplied with P and P + N did not differ in biomass from those grown with only deionized water. This may be due to the availability of nutrients upon soil sterilization.

The results of the VAM treatments suggest that colonization by VAM fungi may be a carbon drain on the plant. However, this may be true only during

early growth of rice (land not flooded), when VAM fungi are colonizing young plants not yet fully established. It is possible that older, established rice plants in flooded fields may show a different response to VAM fungal colonization.

In all cases where nutrients were supplied, colonization of rice roots was significantly lower than that in roots of plants supplied with deionized water. It is

possible that higher availability of nutrients to plant roots depressed VAM fungal colonization. Other studies have suggested this depression in colonization may be due to the reduction of exudate leakage and/or the greater availability of inorganic nutrients in the rhizosphere.

The high biomass of plants in the deionized water treatment may be due to

higher VAM fungal colonization in this treatment.

This study suggests that VAM fungi may have a detrimental effect on early growth of rice, reducing establishment. This relationship may change as rice plants grow and become better established. The significance of the roles of VAM fungi and inorganic fertilizer needs further investigation. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 on rice seedlings and grain yield

Guang Jian Liang, Biology Department, Xijiang University, Zhaoqing, P.O. Box 526061, China

Paclobutrazol (Pac) treatment reduces rice seedling height in summer and lodging in autumn, but does not significantly increase yields.

We evaluated the effect on yield of applying Pac alone and in a mixture with KH_2PO_4 to rice seedlings. All treated plants were shorter, had wider seedling base, and more tillers than untreated controls.

Pac alone did not increase the height of the first tiller, production of new roots after transplanting, yield components, or yield. Pac plus KH_2PO_4 , however, increased first tiller height and new root

Table 1. Effect of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 application on rice seedlings. Zhaoqing, China, 1988-89 early season.

Treatment	Seedlings		Tillers (no./seedling)	1st tiller length (cm)	New roots ^a (no./plant)
	Height (cm)	Base width (mm)			
	<i>Shan You 2</i>				
Control	32	4.0	0.6	15.0	3
270 ppm Pac	27	4.5	2.0	17.5	4
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	29	5.8	2.5	22.0	5
LSD (P = 0.05)	2	0.6	1.1	3.0	2
	<i>Shan You 63</i>				
Control	28	3.6	2.3	11.5	4
270 ppm Pac	24	4.5	3.0	12.5	5
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	25	5.4	3.8	19.2	7
LSD (P = 0.05)	2	0.6	1.0	3.0	2

^a Measured 5 d after transplanting.

Table 2. Effect of paclobutrazol and KH_2PO_4 application on grain yield and yield components.^a Zhaoqing, China, 1988-89 late season.^a

Treatment	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
	<i>Shan You 2</i>			
Control	297	106	27.0	8.5
270 ppm Pac	296	105	27.6	8.6
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	306	108	28.0	9.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	7.5	4.0	0.9	0.4
	<i>Shan You 63</i>			
Control	292	116	28.1	9.5
270 ppm Pac	295	114	28.2	9.2
270 ppm Pac + 30 ppm KH_2PO_4	300	122	29.0	10.6
LSD (P = 0.05)	7.8	4.2	0.8	0.4

Fertilized with 225 kg N, 66 kg P, 149 kg K/ha.

number (Table 1), thereby increasing the capacity for absorption of mineral nutrients.

As a result, panicle number, filled grain number, and 1,000-grain weight increased.

Shan You 63 yielded 10.6 t/ha in the late season (Table 2), a new record in a 200,000-ha area of Zhaoqing. ■

Fertilizer management

Effect of straw + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ application on rice

Jian Luo and Zhi-wu Huang, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, China

We studied the influence of C:N ratio and preflooding on rice growth and production when rice straw was applied with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in a greenhouse pot experiment, 1988 late season.

Pearl River alluvial soil (medium loam, pH 6.5, 0.15% total N, 2.5% organic C, CEC 14 meq/100 g soil) was air dried and screened, and placed in pottery pots at 5 kg/pot. Superphosphate (5.0 g/pot) and KCl (2.0 g/pot) were basally applied. Rice straw (0.72% total N, C:N ratio 53) of 0, 9.8, 37.3, and 127.1 g, respectively, needed to establish 0, 10, 25, or 40 C:N ratio was thoroughly mixed with the soil. N (300 mg) as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution was banded 5 cm deep into each pot in an 8-cm-diameter circle. The pots were preflooded at 2, 4, or 6 wk, and 9 seedlings/pot transplanted. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design.

Preflooding had no significant effects on tiller number, panicle dry weight, or